

ATTENTION TO WOMEN AND GIRLS IN THE SOCIAL SOCIETY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

To increase the socio-political activity of women in our country, to create conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and industries, to ensure unconditional observance of their rights and legal interests, to protect motherhood and childhood in all aspects. Extensive work is being done to support and strengthen the family institution.

Key words: Women, socio-political activity, motherhood and childhood, family institution.

It has been repeatedly discussed in the world community that increasing the activity of women and girls in all aspects of social, political and economic life, providing them with education and professional skills and ensuring their employment is the main strategic goal of every developing country. Today, international organizations are also implementing a number of measures regarding the formation of social relations and social protection of women. If we look at the whole world, one of the main issues in developed and developing countries is about "Gender equality". Even influential organizations are not indifferent to the fate of women today. If we turn our attention to the United Nations Organization, it pays special attention to the issue of "Gender Equality". Nowadays, increasing the role of women in the life of society is becoming an urgent topic. Active participation of women and girls in state management and the creation of a number of privileges for them is a set of reforms implemented by our state today. As we talk about the opportunities given to women by the society, democratic principles began to be formed after the independence of our country. As a proof of this, we can see the opportunities given to women by the state. Yes, it must be admitted that during the time of the former Soviets, women and girls were hardly paid attention to, their duties were limited only to housework. Mental and physical violence against women, which is practically not protected by law. Of course, this is the bitter truth of history! The society did not provide opportunities for women-girls to get education, on the contrary, they were busy repressing knowledgeable, superstitious, intelligent, ambitious people, our women were not able to take their place in the society. . When our country just gained independence, the activities of women and girls in the life of the society were hardly noticed. With the development of democratic principles, concepts such as gender equality, involvement of women and girls in the scene of active society, protection of their rights and freedoms, social support of needy women and girls, employment provision, widespread involvement in entrepreneurship, and state awards named after Zulfia came into being. . According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 1995 "On measures to increase the role of women and girls in the construction of the state and society", the role of women and girls in the life of society will be increased. As proof of this, the

chairmen of women's committees in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and districts were included in the local authorities. If we look at the reforms of recent years, our state has created great opportunities for women and girls. For example, education loans, women's notebook and so on.

I personally used the preferential education loan for women. It is known that 24 documents aimed at women and girls, including 2 laws, 6 decrees and decisions of the President, and 16 decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers have been adopted in recent years. Currently, women and girls in our country actively participate in all spheres and branches of our life and make an incomparable contribution to building New Uzbekistan. We all know that among them there are deputies and senators, ministers and governors, folk poets, academicians, professors. Today, in our country, structures such as the Commission on Ensuring Gender Equality, the Committee on Women and Girls and Gender Issues of the Oliy Majlis Senate, and the Public Council of Women and Girls of the Republic play an important role in protecting the interests of our sisters. In order to adequately encourage active women in social life, the "Reputable Woman" badge was established, 587 women were awarded, and the activities of 14 regional and 203 district (city) women's public councils were launched. We have many achievements, but we also have a number of shortcomings. The saying of our people, "Where there is work, there will be shortage" is also true at the moment. The opportunities given to women by our government have reached far-off villages. I mean, some women do not know their rights. There are also young people who simply cannot answer the question "What does the Parliament do?" An educated woman has a different approach to raising a child and encourages her child to think more clearly. Such children will grow up to be beneficial to the future of our New Uzbekistan. In the neighboring country, Afghanistan, there are too many big and small problems, and the government is wrapped in its shell and does not pay enough attention to the social and economic relations of the people, and the lack of criticism and analysis within the country makes the country is blocking the rise. As long as democratic principles are not developed, there will be sad tensions in state administration and social life. Metaphorically, the state that holds the balance of the scales equally glorifies the criteria of justice. We must understand that today's world does not distinguish between genders, those who have high thinking potential will definitely have their place in society.

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